

Article

Data Assimilated Atmospheric Forecasts for Digital Twin of the Ocean Applications: A Case Study in the South Aegean, Greece

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Abstract: This study investigated advancements in atmospheric forecasting by integrating real-time observational data into the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model through the WRF-Data Assimilation (WRF-DA) framework. By refining atmospheric models, we aimed to improve regional high-resolution wave and hydrodynamic forecasts essential for environmental management. Focused on southern Greece, including Crete, the study applied a 3D-Var assimilation technique within WRF, downscaling forecasting data from the Global Forecast System (GFS) to resolutions of 9 km and 3 km. The results showed a 4.7% improvement in wind speed predictions, with significant gains during forecast hours 26–72, enhancing model accuracy across METAR validation locations. These results underscore the positive impact of the integration of additional observational data on model accuracy. This study also highlights the utility of refined atmospheric models for real-world applications through their use in forcing ocean circulation and wave models and subsequent Digital Twin of the Ocean applications. Two such applications—optimal ship routing to minimize CO₂ emissions and oil spill trajectory forecasting to mitigate marine pollution—demonstrate the practical utility of improved models through what-if scenarios in easily deployable, containerized formats.

Keywords: data assimilation; digital twin; dynamic downscaling; oil spill forecasting; optimal ship routing; WRF-DA; NEMO; Wavewatch III

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1. Introduction

The South Aegean is an economically and environmentally significant region [1] with complex topography and physical characteristics [2]. Accurate weather and ocean-wave forecasts are essential to support a range of Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) applications [3], i.e., interoperable models that aim in the digital representation of the ocean physical environment, such as harbor/ship-routing safety assessment, marine pollution management, and more [4]. To enhance forecast accuracy, data assimilation (DA) techniques are employed by integrating in situ observations into numerical models [5].

In the South Aegean, the availability of atmospheric (near) real-time in situ datasets significantly surpasses that of oceanic data. This limited availability of oceanographic data, combined with the large dimensionality and non-linearity of ocean-wave models, introduces data uncertainties that can limit the efficiency of DA [6]. Ocean circulation and wave models are particularly sensitive to wind field selection [7–9], as wind fields play a critical role in determining the momentum and heat fluxes that drive these systems. Correcting atmospheric input can potentially improve predictions of ocean circulation and wave models [10,11]. These factors highlight the importance of DA-enhanced atmospheric forecasts.

Numerous DA techniques exist to improve atmospheric numerical models. Among the most widely used are three-dimensional variational DA (3D-Var) [12], four-dimensional

variational DA (4D-Var) [13,14] and sequential methods such as the Kalman filter and hybrid methodologies combining them with variational methods [15], ensemble Kalman filter [16], and ensemble optimal interpolation [17]. Variational methods process all observations holistically, providing a more consistent and coherent estimate of the model state [14]. Sequential methods, on the other hand, process observations as they are collected, making them more adaptable to real-time data [18]. Although sequential methods can be preferred in real-time operational forecasting due to their ability to handle fluctuating data availability, they are prone to transmitting observational noise, which can reduce the precision of the estimated state [19].

For this study, the 3D-Var method was selected as it is computationally less expensive—an important factor given the operational daily cycle [12]. It is also less demanding in terms of data requirements, making it suitable for the sparse real-time in situ datasets available in this region, and it performs well for both short-term and longer forecasting horizons [20].

The main aim of this study was to cost-effectively correct the atmospheric forecasting model in the South Aegean for use as input in DTO applications where DA cannot be performed. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology of the DA applied to the atmospheric model and details the DTO model specifics. The 3D-Var results along with the DTO model results using the corrected atmospheric forecast in comparison to the original one are presented in Section 3. Discussion of the results, along with demonstration of further DTO applications, are showcased in Section 4.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Case Study and Data Availability

The area of interest is geographically focused around the island of Crete, in the south of Greece, an area of high economic interest and human activity as the Heraklion port is the third highest passenger traffic port in Greece, with strategic positioning as it interconnects three continents (Europe, Asia, and Africa) [1]. Thus, perspective users of the marine tools created for better marine planning, accident avoidance, decrease in CO₂ emitted by ships, etc., can include but are not limited to the Hellenic Coast Guard, port authorities, coastal municipalities, ship owners and companies, citizens, etc. The users of those tools require a Digital Twin of the Ocean solution that offers validated, high-resolution information and services; accurate short-term forecasts; decision support; early warnings; and alerts. To that end, we describe improvements to the models that are being made in our case study, as well as their integration with such DTO tools for thematic applications.

The initial forcing for the operational Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) is derived in real time from the Global Forecast System (GFS) forecasting model by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) (2015) that provides forecasts with a spatial resolution of approximately 27 km × 27 km and a temporal resolution of 6 h, being extremely coarse for observing fine-scale wind phenomena [21]. As seen in Figure 1, the domain of interest is dynamically downscaled two times, firstly to a 9 km × 9 km grid named D01, and then to a 3 km × 3 km finer grid centered around Crete (D02).

Firstly, we introduce the available data sources for the area of interest, for both initializing the models with relevant forcing data and observational data that are used for DA and validation of the models. The area of interest is the South Aegean Sea; the Cretan Sea; part of the border region of the Ionian Sea; and the Levantine Sea surrounding the island of Crete, Greece. The two nested subdomains of the WRF program are shown in Figure 1. The available data are as follows:

Figure 1. The two downscaled domains of interest for the WRF application in southern Greece. Ground METAR stations are indicated by blue dots. Red dots are buoy locations, and orange signifies additional CretaWeather Meteorological stations used for DA. Coordinates of the bounding box are shown around the domain, with indications on inner and outer domain D01–D02, as well as (a) a zoomed map of Antikythera Island with the 3 km grid (grey) and 9 km grid (red) overlay.

Data Source I: Cretaweather.gr offers in situ data information in high temporal resolution (5 min) in available stations. Additional station locations from CretaWeather are marked in Figure 1 as orange dots.

Data Source II: NOAA METAR ISH ground data: NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information (2001): Global Surface Hourly (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/search/index>, last accessed online 28 October 2024). These data were accessed through the RNOAA library, which downloads and updates real-time data from the NOAA ISD-ISH database. This dataset is curated by NOAA, so each observation is accompanied with control flags that indicate its quality, and the stations' uptime is monitored to reduce missing value cases.

Data Source III: CMEMS Marine Data store to download the in situ data near real time from the "copernicusmarinetoolbox" API (<https://help.marine.copernicus.eu/en/articles/7949409-copernicus-marine-toolbox-introduction>, last accessed online 28 October 2024), product: Mediterranean Sea—near real-time (NRT) in situ quality-controlled observations, hourly updated and distributed by INSTAC within 24–48 h from acquisition on average (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/INSITU_MED_PHYBGCWAV_DISCRETE_MYNRT_013_035/description, last accessed online 28 October 2024).

Data Source IV: For the initialization of WRF with external atmospheric forcing, the NCEP operational GFS analysis and forecasts were used as the initial meteorological fields for the simulation. The data are 0.25-degree spatial resolution that correspond to approximately 27 km. More information about the dataset can be found in [22]. The WRF model is initially run without the application of DA and is henceforth referred to as the Control run, with downscaling of the computational grid at D01 (9 km grid) and at D02 (3 km grid) in the domains outlined in Figure 1.

As seen, the data available in the coarser domain D01 that measure oceanic variables (Data Source III, Section 2.1) are limited to 4 locations, which drop down to 2 for the finer resolution subdomain D02, and that can be used for validation. This makes the creation, calibration, and validation of such a system extremely difficult. To overcome this, additional data that have never been used before to the authors' knowledge have been added in the form of atmospheric data (Data Source I, Section 2.1), and the observational network uses meteorological stations similar to [23].

2.2. 3D/4D-Var Techniques

The goal of any variational DA technique is to find the optimal state x , henceforth called “analysis”, that minimizes a cost function [24]. For the case of the 3D-Var method, the main differentiation being that it is a time-independent method that is less computationally demanding and requires less data but may suffer from accurately capturing fast evolving weather systems. However, it can provide accurate results for more slowly time-paced variables and is still useful for many practical applications due to the low computational cost. The method can be summarized in minimizing functional J with respect to the Analysis state x in the following cost function [12]:

$$J(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[(x - x^b)^T B^{-1} (x - x^b) + (y - H(x))^T R^{-1} (y - H(x)) \right], \quad (1)$$

where superscripts T , -1 are the standard notation for transpose and inverse operators; x^b is the background state or field (previous forecast or initialization); and y is the observation vector. $H(x)$ is the observation operator that maps the model variable to the observation space, introducing additional representation errors. Additionally, this method requires the estimation of the background and observation error covariance matrices (B , R), respectively. The computation of the observation and most importantly the background error covariance matrices is a heavily discussed and researched topic (see, e.g., [13,20,24,25]). The approach for estimating matrix B for the case study considered here is discussed in the next sections.

The extension of 3D-Var is named 4D-Var, which similarly to 3D-Var solves an optimization problem, with the main difference being that it considers data over specific time bins, which allows it to account for the temporal evolution of the atmosphere, in contrast to the 3D-Var that is not time dependent, and it considers a single analysis time by assimilating observations from that specific time into the model. This difference makes the 4D-Var more computationally intensive due to the use of the fully nonlinear model and consideration of the entire assimilation window. Hence, it makes it more suitable for research and high-performance computing environments, whereas the 3D-Var can be easier implemented for operational purposes [12,26], and it can be used to correct the initial and boundary conditions of the outer domain in an operational setting. In equation form, 4D-Var considers the splitting of the time dimension in discretized n time-bins, and the observations y_i that belong to each time bin are used. So, Equation (1) is transformed into

$$J(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[(x - x^b)^T B^{-1} (x - x^b) + \sum_i^n (y_i - H_i(x_i))^T R^{-1} (y_i - H_i(x_i)) \right], \quad (2)$$

where the observational last term on the right hand side is a sum over all time bins [14].

Variational methods offer an advantage over sequential techniques by achieving a state x that effectively assimilates all available observations simultaneously through the minimization of J . However, the use of variational data assimilation comes with certain drawbacks, most notably its reliance on several assumptions, with a main one being that the error statistics do not propagate in time [26]. This leads to a very strong reliance of the assimilation results on the background error calculation, which is often hard to accurately quantify. The precision of prescribed errors becomes pivotal for the accuracy of the resulting analysis, given that imperfect observations and prior information are integral inputs in the assimilation process [25]. The last limitation is shared with sequential DA techniques.

Additionally, while the variational approach allows for the incorporation of linearized dynamical and physical processes, it is crucial to acknowledge that real errors within the Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) system can exhibit highly nonlinear behavior. This poses a challenge for variational data assimilation, especially in scenarios characterized by strong nonlinearity, such as convective scale or tropical weather systems. Recognizing this limitation has led to the development of hybrid methodologies with varying resolutions to address challenges in specific weather scenarios. For instance, Liu, Ban, Hong, and Kuo [13] introduced a multi-resolution incremental 4D-Var technique for operational purposes. This

approach reduces computational requirements since the data assimilation system and the WRF model forecast are not required to have a common resolution. Last but not least, a primary drawback of variational techniques lies in their significant computational cost. This is particularly evident in the computation of the inverse of matrix B , a matrix with dimensions $(n \cdot m) \times (n \cdot m)$, where n and m represent the number of grid points in the X and Y dimensions of the model, respectively. In high-resolution regional models, this computational burden can quickly become impractical. The time required for this process must be carefully managed, especially in operational settings where the improved forecast must be generated within a timeframe typically not exceeding a day, aligning with the re-run schedule of our operational setup. For the above reasons, the method applied in this case study is the 3D-Var.

2.3. Configuration Set-Up

The weather forecasts were conducted using WRF (WRF-4.4), with data assimilation executed by the WRF Data Assimilation model (WRF-DA-4.4). WRF is capable of delivering atmospheric simulations appropriate for a wide array of applications, while WRF-DA generates the analysis—integrating ground-based observations to produce perturbed initial and boundary conditions for WRF. Both models were configured to offer a coupled system of high spatial resolution analysis and forecasts covering southern Greece. The WRF model was initialized at 00 UTC and ran daily with a ramp-up period of 24 h, forecasting the next 72 h. This will henceforth be referred to as the forecasting horizon. More details on similar WRF runs and the parametrizations made for the specific test case are presented in [21], but with different forcing data, so an additional validation is performed here to establish the baseline control case run. The nesting configuration is illustrated schematically in Figure 1.

Concerning the WRF-DA preprocessing, the system requires the observations to be translated into littleR format, which is a specific ASCII-based file format (<https://www2.mmm.ucar.edu/wrf/users/wrfda/OnlineTutorial/Help/littler.html>, last accessed online 28 October 2024). Then, the littleR files are processed through the WRF preprocessor, and the observational errors are calculated depending on the category of the sensor that is reported in the littleR file (SYNOP, BUOY, etc.), as well as the prescribed height of measurement, elevation, and pressure. It is assumed that the errors of the field measurements are statistically independent of each other, so the observational covariance matrix R is diagonal, and its values represent each sensor's instrumental error [12], suggested by the WRF-DA suite. Quality control of the observations was carried out so that outliers, duplicates, and observations that are not in the analyzed space–time window were removed. A crucial part of the accuracy of any variational DA technique is the approximation of the covariance matrix B , as shown in Equations (1) and (2). There are two methods implemented within WRF-DA to approximate the matrix B : the Ensemble method (ENS) and the climatological approach known as the National Meteorological Center method (NMC), introduced by Parrish and Derber [27]. The Ensemble method uses ensemble perturbations from a given set of forecasts. However, for regional studies, the NMC method is more commonly used. Since our model has been run operationally on a daily basis, forecasting four days in each run, the overlapping forecasted days from different simulations can be utilized to approximate the model error, denoted by ϵ_b . This procedure assumes that background errors can be effectively represented by statistical data derived from averaged forecast differences, typically from a series of month-long forecasts with 36 h and 12 h validity at the same time. This concept is expressed in the following equation form:

$$B = \overline{(x^b - x^t)(x^b - x^t)^T} = \overline{\epsilon_b \epsilon_b^T} \cong \overline{(x^{i+36} - x^{i+12})(x^{i+36} - x^{i+12})^T}, \quad (3)$$

where x^t is the unknown true atmospheric state, and the use of an overbar signifies the average over all samples that are collected beforehand for the estimation of the background error. The subtracted states x^{i+36}, x^{i+12} are all the forecasted outputs that co-occur and originate from a specific WRF simulation that has been run 1 day apart [28]. This is carried out by

the following utility: https://github.com/wrf-model/GENBE_2.0 (last accessed online 28 October 2024). To approximate this matrix, simulations are performed for 2-month periods during winter and summer conditions separately, and they are used to assimilate data in each period accordingly, as it has been shown to affect the accuracy of the DA [20]. One major drawback of this technique is that the background error covariances are estimated offline and have similar characteristics to climatological statistics, which do not evolve with time and hence are not flow-dependent. While the NMC method described is computationally efficient [20], it can occasionally lead to a minimal influence of the 3D-Var on the background field, or potentially exacerbate the results relative to actual observations. To address this issue, the objective is to employ distinct background covariances contingent upon the season, as previously described. Additionally, if the accuracy does not meet satisfactory thresholds, using a similar analysis that we present in Section 3, adjustments can be made to the temporal window that is considered for the creation of covariance matrix B.

2.4. Algorithmic Process of WRF-DA 3D-Var

After calculating the covariance matrix B (be.dat in WRF terms) and first guess (fg for WRF notation) files, one has to update the namelist of WRF to compute the corrected initial state. The complete algorithmic flow chart is shown in Figure 2, where the order of operations one must follow to achieve a corrected WRF forecast is outlined for the 3D-Var technique specifically. To summarize the process of WRF-DA, one begins by creating initial conditions for WRF (wrfinput) through the WRF Preprocessing System (WPS). This step uses the GFS meteorological fields described in Data Sources IV (Section 2.1). The next step involves applying WRF-DA to the generated wrfinput file, assimilating observational data to produce a refined wrfvar_output file, which serves the purpose of an updated data-assimilated wrfinput. Subsequently, to ensure consistency with the new initial conditions, the boundary conditions need to be updated for the entire forecast period.

Figure 2. WRF-DA flow chart adapted by [21] with boundary condition (BC) update for all time-steps based on the new analysis computed by WRF-DA. This update was performed on the outer parent

domain D01 with the 9 km resolution. The WRF output was then used to force hydrodynamic and wave forecasting models. B and R are the background and observational error covariance matrices, and x_b , x , and y are the background field, analysis field, and observation vector, respectively, as seen in Equation (1).

Noted by dotted lines in Figure 2, there is an explanation of how boundary conditions are updated using the analysis x at time step t instead of the initial background field x^b as seen in Equation (1), and then how the background field at time step $(t + dt)$ is updated in subsequent time steps using a perturbed time derivative $(\text{Field}(t + dt) - \text{Analysis}(t))/dt$. Since the denominator includes dt (the time increment), as the time interval between the analysis time t and each subsequent step increases, the effect of the data assimilation (DA) analysis at step t on the boundary condition diminishes. This is expected, as the influence of observations at the initialization time on the model should naturally decrease over time. In the whole flow chart, the respective steps are color-coded with their explanation for the readers' convenience.

Finally, the process concludes with the execution of WRF to generate a new downscaled forecast in all nested subdomains (D01 and D02 in Figure 1). We note that the process mentioned applies only to the parent WRF domain D01, since the initial and boundary conditions for the child domain D02 are inherited by interpolating the values from the parent domain D01 [29]. Then, this updated forecast can be used as alternative forcing for a range of applications, which in our case are based on wave and hydrodynamic forecasting.

To address the elevated computational demands typically associated with variational methods, the solver chosen for minimizing the functional in Equation (1) is the iterative conjugate gradient. In comparison to alternative optimization methods available within the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) framework, such as the quasi-Newton approach, the conjugate gradient method is deemed less computationally demanding. Additionally, preconditioning through WRF-DA options are employed as described in the introduction article of WRF 3D-Var to mitigate the computational complexities associated with inverting the correlation matrix B [12]. The strategic utilization of the conjugate gradient solver and preconditioning techniques contributes to the enhanced computational tractability of the overall variational methodology [30].

2.5. Performance Metrics

The error metrics that are used to validate the atmospheric models using observational data from the closest meteorological stations to the computational grid, employing the nearest neighbor algorithm, are presented. Additionally, the same metrics are used for the comparative analysis of the DA model and its control case counterpart, which is the downscaled model without any data used to correct it.

A strong statistical framework was created to back up the analysis mentioned above. The following error metrics have been summarized in [31] and are the most regularly utilized in a variety of various disciplines (for example, weather prediction and hydrology) where models are validated using observational data.

(a) The bias and absolute bias metric

$$BIAS = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (M_i - O_i) = \bar{M} - \bar{O}, \quad (4)$$

where N denotes the number of records, M the model prediction, and O the observation records. This statistical parameter provides information in a standard way about systematic errors, i.e., the tendency of the model to overestimate or underestimate the predicted values. BIAS serves as a measure of differences between observations and model predictions, with ideal values closer to zero. Note that bias can be positive or negative, indicating overprediction or underprediction. Sometimes it is of more use to calculate the absolute value of the difference of measured and observed values, which will henceforth be referred to as absolute bias.

(b) Root mean squared error (RMSE)

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (M_i - O_i)^2}{N}}, \quad (5)$$

RMSE (root mean squared error) is utilized as a measure of the variability of the error and offers an indication of the efficacy of the model to predict the general behavior of the system. The ideal value is 0, and the lower the better applies [32].

(c) **The correlation coefficient:**

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N ((x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y}))}{(\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2)^{1/2}}, \quad (6)$$

which measures the linear correlation between forecasts (y_i) and observations (x_i) and takes values lower or equal to 1, with the higher values being the better ones [31,32].

2.6. Digital Twin of the Ocean Components

Regional high-resolution ocean circulation and wave forecasting models require accurate atmospheric forcing inputs [33]. WRF-DA outputs are used as inputs in a regional configuration based on the Nucleus for European Modeling of the Ocean (NEMO v3.6) framework, which solves the primitive equations [34]. The configuration's domain covers the surrounding area of the Cretan Island (Cretan Sea and part of the Levantine Sea; 22.993–26.925° E and 34.4218–36.0915° N), with a horizontal grid resolution of ~1 km and 72 vertical levels, with a decreasing resolution from the surface to the bottom from 1 m to 191 m (deepest point 4695.7 m). For the open boundary conditions surrounding the domain, forecast data from the CMEMS platform were used (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013/description last accessed online 28 October 2024).

WRF-DA outputs were also used as inputs in a regional configuration based on the Wavewatch III (WWIII) wave model [35], surrounding the area of 22.705–27.457° E, 33.95–36.81° N.

3. Results

We here introduce and comment on the results, firstly validating the dynamical downscaling control case study that featured the implementation of the WRF. Results of the application of 3D-Var to the case study are discussed, for a test case consisting of a time period of 92 days with a forecast horizon of 3 days each. The respective dates cover a summer case from 15 July 2024 to 15 October 2024 in order to show the improvement and highlight the challenges associated with this task. For consistency purposes, this time window is also used to compare the impact that the atmospheric DA has on wave and hydrodynamic modelling when used as alternative forcing.

This study presents the implementation of the 3D-Var technique within a WRF-DA model framework, focusing on a case study encompassing the region around the island of Crete. The model is configured to correct daily runs of 3-day forecasts over a 3-month period. A notable challenge highlighted in Section 2 is the substantial computational burden associated with this approach, necessitating intricate parameter optimization. Specifically, the computational demands are exemplified by a customized WRF run, where the initial 27 km input forcing undergoes dynamical downscaling to spatial resolutions of 9 km and 3 km through consecutive one-way nesting procedures. This process, executed on an Intel Xeon cluster with 64 cores, requires approximately 5 h to complete. Subsequently, real-time data acquisition, transformation into "littleR" format files, and functional minimization entail an additional half-hour on the same cluster. The subsequent assimilated run demands another 5 h of computational time, employing MPI parallelization between the CPU cores.

To achieve reliable results, a significant number of daily runs, specifically 92, was considered in this study in order to mitigate statistical errors. Furthermore, there are many tunable parameters in this methodology that are case specific, for example, VAR_SCALING,

a multiplier to the background error parameter since it is seen to be often underestimated, was proposed in the work of [20] as equal to 3, but in our case, this showed a deterioration of the results, indicating that the background error was not overestimated in our case. Fine-tuning these parameters was performed solely through trial and error, requiring significant computational resources and time. While only small differences were observed, the best configuration was selected for operational use in our tests. It is important to note that model calibration is an ongoing process, and most forecast data providers continuously perform and update their calibrations to enhance their services. Additionally, the reliable selection of observation points that provided a continuous stream of observations without missing values was of the essence, and the only way to overcome this burden is with continuous testing and validation through observational data.

This validation poses additional challenges, notably the discretization error arising from the fact that observation points and model nodes do not typically coincide. The proximity of meteorological stations to model grid points influences the validation process, with errors persisting unless a more refined model is introduced, which introduces additional points in the finer grid and reduces the distance from the model's grid point to the observational one. This approach increases the computational cost and time, which can become a computational burden when considering operational forecasting systems that run on a continuous schedule.

To ensure that the model approximates the real atmospheric conditions and is able to forecast without the resolution handicapping the forecasting skill, we performed a comparative analysis between the 27 km spatial resolution forcing used to initialize the WRF model and the 3 km dynamically downscaled model, which is then mentioned as the control case in our subsequent step of data integration within the WRF-DA model.

3.1. Downscaled Model Validation

The metrics, which are shown in Table 1, were the BIAS, RMSE, and correlation coefficient, and concluded with a definitive improvement on average of all the stations. The validation ran operationally for the first 6 months of the year 2023, considering daily forecast runs with a 1 day ramping-up period and 3-day forecasting horizon, and we averaged the results in hindcast mode by collecting observations from the nine METAR stations that fell within the bounding box area of the finer and smaller domain of 3 km (D02), as seen in Figure 1, but eventually removing three stations that did not offer a continuous data stream in the same 3 h resolution that the other six had. Although anomalies, such as those observed at the SAMOS station, may arise, they did not negate the overall enhancement that the dynamically downscaled 3 km model shows, as evidenced by metric averaging across all stations. Thus, in the last line, we averaged the error metrics of all available stations, finding all three of the considered metrics to favor the downscaled model.

Table 1. Comparison of error values for the GFS model, which was run with a 27 km spatial resolution and WRF 3 km downscaled model on wind speed data utilizing the BIAS, RMSE, and correlation coefficient metrics for the first six months of 2023 (the better result is denoted with a bold font).

Station Name	BIAS		RMSE		Correlation Coefficient	
	GFS (27 km)	WRF (3 km)	GFS (27 km)	WRF (3 km)	GFS (27 km)	WRF (3 km)
SAMOS	−1.276	−1.751	4.415	3.451	0.242	0.008
SYROS	−1.060	−0.299	4.804	3.844	0.048	0.332
EL VENIZELOS	−2.578	−1.515	5.250	3.915	0.029	0.400
NIKOS KAZANTZAKIS	−2.922	−0.490	5.676	4.063	0.127	0.210
KARPATOS (AIRPORT)	−0.368	0.202	4.132	4.000	0.271	0.259
PAROS	−3.258	−0.968	5.706	3.510	0.268	0.371

More specifically, the validation of the downscaled atmospheric model, as shown in Table 1, demonstrated a notable improvement of approximately 24% in RMSE, averaged across all stations. The bias improvement cannot be expressed as a percentage, given that bias encompasses both positive and negative values, indicating when the model overpredicts (positive bias) or underpredicts (negative bias). Correlation coefficients were computed at each individual validation station, showing larger values indicating better performance in all but two stations.

This underscores the significance of higher-resolution models in enhancing atmospheric forecasting accuracy in practical applications. However, it is important to note that the efficacy of such models is contingent upon various factors, including downscaling ratio [13], terrain, and orographic resolution [36], which may vary across different test cases.

Following the successful validation of the 3 km WRF hereby mentioned as the Control case study, we proceeded by introducing the operational parametrizations for the 3D-Var case, subsequently comparing the extent of improvement observed, using the Control case as a reference. To be able to express the improvement of the models percentagewise, the remaining comparative results between the control and 3D-Var cases are presented in terms of absolute bias.

3.2. 3D-Var Results

The presentation of DA results underscores the persistent challenge in refining wind speed forecasts, despite advancements in assimilation techniques. Wind speed stands out as a critical variable for subsequent wave and hydrodynamic models. A test case was examined, incorporating all available data sources (I, II, and III, Section 2.1) whenever they were available, augmenting the NOAA METAR and POSEIDON Buoys dataset with approximately 30 meteorological stations situated across the island of Crete. The inclusion of additional observation locations was anticipated to significantly enhance accuracy, demonstrating a path towards improved forecasting precision. Notably, not all stations seen in Figure 1 always have availability of data to be assimilated, and hence we only included in each run the stations that had data availability closer to the analysis time, which is the time of the simulation when the functional J from Equation (1) is minimized (here we used the 00:00 of the hindcast day).

In Figure 3, the plot shows the absolute bias for wind speed for both the case of the control simulation (WRF without any DA) and the corrected one with the 3D-Var, under the dynamically downscaled 3 km spatial resolution. The predicted values at each case were compared to the corresponding observations by the six METAR stations of Dataset II, and these biases were plotted with representative values across 3 months of daily simulations for each forecast hour in 3-hourly temporal resolution that most METAR data showcased, with their mean values shown in stars. Additionally, their 90th percentiles over the 92 simulations are shown with the shaded same color areas. Those simulations fall within mostly summer period in Greece, performed during the months of mid-July to mid-October 2024, and hence the covariance matrix that was calculated for the summer period was used.

As the lower value translates to improved model in absolute bias terms, we observed that between forecast hours 26 and 72, the mean values as well as the percentiles for the 3D-Var case were consistently lower than the control case. Evidently, calculating the average percentagewise improvement from the control simulations to the 3D-Var case, for all simulations in the wind speed variable compared to the observational data, we found a 5.6% improvement, whereas the overall improvement for all forecast hours was calculated at 4.7%.

Figure 3. Absolute bias statistics for 3 months from 15/7/2024 to 15/10/2024, comparing Control and 3D-Var for each forecast hour 1–72. Blue and red shading indicate the 90th percentile across all simulations, and stars are the mean value of the errors for 10 m wind speed, compared to the observed value at each station.

This finding is consistent with [20], which features a 3D-Var study with dynamical downscaling in the southern region of China, which also demonstrated bigger contributions of the 3D-Var around the middle of the forecast horizon period. In comparison with their study, our case study showcased comparable improvement percentages, although in our case, we had considerably less observational data coverage. Specifically, in our wider D01 region shown in Figure 1, there were approximately 30 METAR stations provided by the NOAA ISD/ISH dataset, which were mostly consistently available throughout the simulation period, the nearly 40 stations of Data Source IV as well as 4 buoys from Data Source III (Section 2.1), compared to the study of [20] that featured more than 300 METAR stations and resulted in an average improvement in 10 m wind speeds of about 4% throughout their entire forecast horizon.

Additionally, in Figure 4, a bar chart is presented depicting absolute biases for each station utilized in the validation process from the METAR data that were used for validation purposes. Note that some METAR stations that were used for DA were not used for validation, since the specific 3D-Var technique implemented requires data availability only during the analysis time, whereas for validation, we used the entire forecasting horizon. Furthermore, some stations had available data with a coarser 6 h temporal resolution instead of the 3 hourly that we calculated for the errors of Figure 3. Hence, for consistency, the six stations shown in Table 1 and Figure 4 are retained as validation stations.

This analysis reveals that all stations except SAMOS exhibited an improvement in wind speed over the 3 month period selected for validation. It is noteworthy that the errors shown in Figure 4 could include systematic errors in the model originating from the geometrical discretization but could also be due to the spatial validation mechanism that was chosen to be the nearest neighbor from the observation location to the grid points. Since the resolution of the finer model under examination was 3 km, this discrepancy could result in a significant difference of the model value with the METAR measurement. Nevertheless, METAR comparisons are a widely used validation method for such applications [21] and should be taken as an indicative measure averaged across all available stations, as shown in Figure 3, for multiple daily simulations, which introduces a degree of difficulty in the

calibration of proposed models, as the computational cost for each simulation is high, as previously discussed.

Figure 4. Absolute bias error metric compared to observations per validation meteorological station in D02 averaged for all forecast hours for wind speed magnitude. Blue and orange indicate control and 3D-Var case, respectively.

Figure 5 is similar to Figure 4 for temperature absolute bias values, where most stations did not show significant improvements, except NIKOS KAZANTZAKIS station, which is the Cretan airport in Heraklion, closest to the assimilated stations from Data Source I (Section 2.1). We note that different variables might have higher errors per validation station, which is attributed to geographic differences that might hinder the model’s performance depending on distance to shore, elevation, mountaneous regions nearby, etc.

Figure 5. Absolute bias error metric compared to observations per validation meteorological station in D02 averaged for all forecast hours for temperature. Blue and orange indicate control and 3D-Var case, respectively.

3.3. Ocean and Wave Model Validation

We performed a validation of the ocean circulation (NEMO) and wave model (WWIII) in Figure 6 for two model set-ups: one that uses WRF atmospheric forcing (Control run) and one that used WRFDA (DA run), for the same time period that the DA validation was performed. A comparison is shown for the values of sea surface temperature (SST) and

significant wave height (SWH) against in situ, satellite, and model reanalysis products. For the in situ dataset, buoy measurements from Data Source III (Section 2.1) falling within the set-up's domain were used. For the satellite comparison, values of the CMEMS SST satellite Level 4 data product (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00172>, last accessed online 28 October 2024), closest to the buoys' coordinates, were used. In the SWH case (Figure 6b), satellite values were not available. For the reanalysis dataset, the coarser resolution (approximately 4 km) CMEMS analysis-forecast products were used (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013/description, https://doi.org/10.25423/cmcc/medsea_analysisforecast_wav_006_017_medwam4, last accessed online 28 October 2024) as a validated model closer to the ground truth. The first day of each daily forecast, for the grid point closest to the buoy coordinates, was considered to reconstruct the time-series shown in Figure 6a of SST (NEMO results) and Figure 6b of SWH (WWIII results) for both model runs that used the WRF and the WRF-DA atmospheric forcing.

Figure 6. Validation of the (a) sea surface temperature (SST) variable computed with Nemo 3.6 (first day of each forecast) forced by WRF Control and Nemo forced by WRF-DA and compared to CMEMS SST (analysis), satellite values, and buoy observations with 3-hourly frequency at the location of the Buoy ID 61277 near Santorini (25.1307° E, 35.7263° N) and (b) sea surface significant wave height of WWIII forced by WRF Control WWIII forced by WRF-DA (first day of each forecast) compared to CMEMS SWH (analysis) and the same buoy measurements.

The SST results (Figure 6a; Table 2) exhibit strong agreement between NEMO outputs (both configurations) and the observational datasets, with the greater discrepancies observed during the summer periods. The addition of WRF-DA as the model's forcing slightly improved the agreement of NEMO with the observational and reanalysis datasets, as reflected by reduced deviations in temporal patterns. Specifically comparing the model results to the BUOY data, the RMSE dropped from 0.52 °C (number of samples, $N = 703$) to 0.49 °C when WRF-DA was included (Table 2). Similarly, for the comparison to the SATELLITE observations, the RMSE decreased from 0.62 °C ($N = 92$) to 0.57 °C when WRF-DA were used (Table 2). Lastly, for the comparison to the CMEMS analysis, the RMSE dropped from 0.62 °C ($N = 2208$) to 0.59 °C with WRF-DA (Table 2). These improvements, albeit small, highlight the benefits of data assimilation in enhancing predictive accuracy in the regional hydrodynamic configuration.

Table 2. Comparison of RMSE values for the entire validation period shown in Figure 6 for the NEMO model–sea surface temperature (SST) variable in °C, compared to BUOY, SATELLITE, and CMEMS (analysis model) as well as forecast values of the WWIII–significant wave height (SWH) variable. Corresponding control and data assimilated (DA) cases signify if the forcing for those models was the control case or from the WRF-DA. N is the number of samples.

Model	Case	BUOY	SATELLITE	CMEMS (Analysis)
NEMO SST	CONTROL	0.52 °C ($N = 703$)	0.62 °C ($N = 92$)	0.62 °C ($N = 2208$)
	DA	0.49 °C ($N = 703$)	0.57 °C ($N = 92$)	0.59 °C ($N = 2208$)
WWIII SWH	CONTROL	0.20 m ($N = 676$)	-	0.21 m ($N = 2208$)
	DA	0.20 m ($N = 676$)	-	0.21 m ($N = 2208$)

The WWIII SWH outputs (both configurations) (Figure 6b) showed good agreement with the observational datasets (BUOY and CMEMS), except at the extreme values. The inclusion of WRF-DA did not lead to significant changes in the model output (Figure 6b; Table 2), where the comparison to the buoy values resulted in RMSE at 0.2 m ($N = 676$), as well as the comparison to the CMEMS product to RMSE = 0.21 m ($N = 2208$) for both model outputs. These values are considered acceptable, given the high variability of the forecasted SWH, which ranged between 0.16 and 2.73 m. Additionally, the results exhibited overall consistency (Figure 6b), which underscores the forecasting ability of the model in diverse conditions. The above indicates the robustness of the model's performance under both configurations.

4. Discussion

The DA results presented in the previous section show that increasing the number of observation locations and incorporating diverse sources enhanced the realism of the downscaled model, even when using the simplest and most computationally efficient variational data assimilation method (3D-Var). The comparison with real observation data and the evaluation of forecast biases over an ensemble of three months of daily runs provide statistically significant results, with improvements observed at wind speed variable at every validation station except SAMOS that provided a consistent, gap-free data stream. More specifically, the test case examined was performed during a mostly summer period in Greece, leading to an overall reduction in wind speed bias from the control case to the 3D-Var one of 4.7%, using the improvements per validation meteorological station of Figure 4 and averaging on all stations, with a 5.6% increase during forecast hours 26–72 for the wind speed variable. For the temperature, mild improvements were noticed in Figure 5, mostly concentrated at the METAR of the Heraklion airport, which was the closest station to the denser network of assimilated meteorological stations from Data Source I (Section 2.1). A comparable reduction of approximately 4% is reported in [20] for the wind speed variable. The model enhancement using data has inherent uncertainties

between studies and can be attributed to both the amount of data assimilated and the differing locations of the validation stations used in each study. As noted in [20], the data employed for DA informs the model upstream by aligning with the direction of the more dominant wind direction, which changes seasonally, considering the average dominant direction. Ideally, it is essential to identify the dominant flow direction and utilize stations positioned to convey information from the point of measurement to the point of validation. This approach enhances model accuracy for various applications. It is important to highlight that this aspect was beyond the scope of our research due to the limited number of observation stations available, even with the addition of stations from Data Source I (Section 2.1). This makes the purpose of this work more evident, as a first step to further improve realism in a regional downscaled model, also maximizing computational efficiency to be able to run it operationally with minimum cost in order to be used as forcing for ocean simulations that enable a more reliable core modelling framework for digital twin applications.

Another potential increase in the accuracy of the enhanced model can be achieved by modifying the data assimilation (DA) methodology, specifically by employing the more computationally demanding and state-of-the-art 4D-Var method (Equation (2)). This method assimilates more data by considering a temporal window for data assimilation. Studies, such as [37], focusing on a similar geographic region, suggest that for wind speed variables, the 3D-Var method might still be superior, despite the 4D-Var analysis focusing on a similar region. While significant enhancements, ranging from a 5 to 10% reduction in mean absolute bias, were observed for temperature fields, the improvement for wind speed remained slightly positive, with reductions ranging from 0.4 to 2% in mean absolute bias, albeit inconsistently across the forecast horizon. Their investigation, conducted during the occurrence of Medicane Ianos in Greece, introduces additional complexity due to the integration of IMERG precipitation data across Europe, which poses further challenges. Nevertheless, these findings highlight the potential benefits of the WRF-DA for operational forecasting systems and contribute to ongoing efforts to optimize and parameterize models for diverse test cases and scenarios.

The validation results of the ocean circulation and wave models (Figure 6) that are based on the data assimilated WRF downscaled model are particularly promising, especially given that the CMEMS model solutions are already corrected with observations through 3D-Var. In contrast, the regional ocean circulation and wave forecasting models operate on an operational cycle, using the aforementioned WRF forcing, which is corrected only with atmospheric data—data that are far more abundant and readily available compared to the limited ocean observations in the area.

Below, two thematic applications are presented that showcase the usefulness of the introduced models on solving real-life problems and offer solutions as containerized applications, with a focus on the ease of use by prospective end-users. The containerization of these tools also aids in the replicability and transferability of the applications, since prospective users can alter input variables and run different what-if scenarios with alternative weather and oceanic conditions, without the need of advanced research knowledge, which contributes to the wider adoption of the tools, which aim at lowering CO₂ emissions and adhering to Green Deal policies, as well as mitigating pollution and enabling safer maritime practices.

4.1. Application to the Optimal Ship Routing Algorithm

Ship weather routing, which involves suggesting low-emission routes, holds significant potential for contributing to the decarbonization of maritime transport [38]. The graph-search VISIR-2 model (discoVerIng Safe and efficient Routes) (<https://zenodo.org/records/10960842>, last accessed online 28 October 2024) incorporates several innovations: refined velocity composition with currents and leeway; no restrictions on vessel type provided the performance curve is available; a cartographic projection, rapid coast intersection screening via a K-dimensional tree; and a least-CO₂ emissions algorithm with dynamic

graph edge weights demonstrating quasi-linear computational performance [39]. Numerical experiments conducted with VISIR-2 in the Mediterranean Sea throughout 2022 [40] utilized Metocean analysis fields and report that for a 125 m ferry, CO₂ savings were calculated at 2% CO₂ compared to the least-distance route on average and up to 49% savings on about 10 days per year with dire weather conditions. VISIR-2 integrates meteorology, oceanography, ocean engineering, and computer science to evaluate the impact of ship routing on decarbonization efforts within the shipping industry. For our case study, Figure 7a demonstrates an indicative example in the Cretan Sea, connecting port of Heraklion to Chania port, utilizing operational downscaled forecasts of 1 × 1 km grid NEMO and WWIII simulations for 5 July 2024. The three alternate routes minimizing distance, time, and CO₂ emissions are shown, along with the time-averaged significant wave height and direction, as well as the sea surface circulation speed and direction throughout the duration of the trip. As is shown, the minimum CO₂ route is southern, utilizing the anticyclonic pattern of the currents during the trip from Heraklion (HER) to Chania (CHA). The route minimizing CO₂ calculated 0.8% less emissions compared to the least distance route, translating in total saving for the trip of approximately 52 kg of CO₂. The example provided is a proof of concept, and it is noted that these results were obtained during non-extreme weather conditions. Additionally, the routes that the higher-resolution models were implemented in were limited to the region where the models were run and constrained by computational cost, which currently do not include the open sea that would have higher waves and a more significant CO₂ savings [39]. This application is freely available in Iliad Marketplace (<https://ocean-twin.eu/marketplace/product/ship-routing>, last accessed online 28 October 2024) with relevant details and links for the prospective end-user to both download forecast data and access application packages that can be adapted for replication of the digital twin application.

(a)

Figure 7. Cont.

Figure 7. Visualization of the DTO application results of (a) a ship routing application simulating the Heraklion to Chania port route and (b) surface oil spill concentration (grey color: tonnes/km²) and beached oil concentration (colored circles) forecasted after 35 h of hypothetical spill release; test case above Heraklion, Greece. Both visuals are available through Geomachine.com (accessed on 28 October 2024).

4.2. Application to Oil Spill Forecasting

Oil spill trajectory forecasting is a complex process that requires both high-resolution forecasting services regarding the ocean and atmospheric states, as well as a model that predicts the transport and weathering of the oil spill. For this application, MEDSLIK II [33,41] (www.medslik-ii.org, last accessed online 28 October 2024) has been utilized, and the whole pipeline description can be easily accessed through Iliad Marketplace (<https://ocean-twin.eu/marketplace/product/oil-spills>, last accessed online 28 October 2024). This on-demand service tool allows users to simulate what-if predictive scenarios and is coupled with an automatic SAR detection tool that can trigger the oil-spill forecasting service. Figure 7b shows an example of such a hypothetical scenario near Heraklion on the Cretan Island, south of Greece. The functionalities of the DTO application allow the user to choose either an instantaneous spill of prespecified oil mass or a continuous spill case, specifying a spill rate and duration.

The front-end of the thematic applications was carried out through the Geomachine platform (www.geomachine.com, last accessed online 28 October 2024). Since the applications are containerized, the next step is to be able to adapt them for use in cloud services, so the user can trigger simulations within the machines that are integrated in Geomachine. The two applications of optimal ship routing and oil spill forecasting are shown in Figure 7 as example cases for the visual front-end.

5. Conclusions

This study explores the application of data assimilation techniques, focusing on operational atmospheric state forecasting. The use of variational methods, particularly WRF-DA 3D-Var, demonstrates potential in refining the WRF model using real-time data. Despite the small observed improvements over the control case, several factors such as discretization errors and localized accumulation of errors in the covariance matrix may contribute to the

limited effectiveness of the 3D-Var correction. Furthermore, the observed improvements with 3D-Var underscore the model's potential for enhancing forecast accuracy.

The small percentage of improvement for WRF-DA can be attributed to several reasons. Firstly, discretization errors may play a role, stemming from the mismatch between model grid points and observation locations, where the nearest neighbor algorithm has been used for direct comparison, and this discrepancy can lead to inaccuracies in the comparison of gridded model data with localized meteorological station data. Secondly, localized accumulation of errors in the covariance matrix B , calculated over a finite time period, may influence the effectiveness of the 3D-Var correction. This suggests a need for further refinement in the estimation of covariance matrices, potentially through prolonged observation periods or enhanced data preprocessing techniques. Lastly, the location of the observation points for assimilation into the model and the validation stations plays a significant role, as implied by [20].

This improved atmospheric model can serve as a foundation for correcting the wave and currents models, illustrating the interconnectedness between atmospheric and sea state modeling. A thorough comparative analysis of the results obtained by the corrected wave model with real-time buoy and in situ meteorological station data will guide the choice of the most suitable approach for operational wave forecasting and atmospheric state data assimilation. This test case, explored in the wider region of the island of Crete, showcases the potential of these refined models in practical applications, thereby contributing to the development of a high-resolution digital twin for ocean applications, demonstrating an on-demand service of optimal ship routing that aids in minimizing CO₂ emissions.

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